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Workpackage WP1-T3

Responsible Partner: Anses

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MATRICE COLLECTION FROM EXPERIMENTAL ANIMAL MODELS

The aim of the Task 3 of work package 1 (WP) was to produce reference parasitic material in animal facilities in definitive and intermediate hosts for their use in other WPs of MEME.

1. Ethical authorizations for animal testing

"ANSES: According to the animal welfare and the experimentation rule, we have the authorization to work on wildlife in our animals facilities in experimentation (decree n° 2013-118 dated 1 February 2013 relating to the protection of animals used for scientific purpose; Order of April 18, 2016 setting the general operating rules for animal breeding facilities for non-domestic animals D54-431-1).

All the authorizations for animal testing have been obtained at ANSES for the infection of mice and foxes with *Echinococcus* parasites. They comply with the ethical authorizations for animal experimentation since 2013 (Decree n° 2013-118 of February 1st 2013) and the ethical authorizations for the experimental infection of carnivores by EM since 2016 (from mice to foxes) (16-073 N° APAFiS: 20160913348095). The ethical authorisation for "Experimental infection of carnivores with *Echinococcus multilocularis*" (Decree n° 21_105#33541 November 16 2021, APAFiS #33541-202110081648536 v11) has been renewed in 2021 for five years.

A new request, also for five years, concerning the ethical authorisation for "experimental infection of mice with larval form of *Echinococcus multilocularis*" is in evaluation course actually under the number 2022011114104529 by the APAFiS comity.

2. Animal facilities

2.1 Mouse

Mice have been kept in animal facilities in compliance with animal welfare, with food and water ad libitum. They were followed daily for health control until euthanasia.

Concerning the rule of 3R (replacement, reduction, refinement). The number of mice used for maintaining the strain has been reduced to 10 mice every 2 months.

The development of protoscoleces succeeded in 60% of mice, the other developed only parasitic mass. To increase welfare of mice in captivity, experimental boxes for 4 to 6 months were enriched by adding mouse house, igloos, paper tubes and pieces wooden.

2.2 Fox

Foxes, the main definitive host for *E. multilocularis*, have been maintained in the animal facilities of ANSES in individual cages. They were fed daily with pet's food and had water ad libitum. To facilitate safety collection of fox feces we have built specific drawers adapted to the cages.

Concerning the rule of 3R (replacement, reduction, refinement). Unfortunately, replacement is not possible according to the fact that we need original form of the parasite (eggs and worm) as reference materials and *in vitro* this is not possible. We have reduce the number of foxes used. For the production of infected faeces, we did not euthanased the foxes. They were kept in specific animal facility for the collection of infected faeces and reused after deworming. For the welfare of foxes and the enrichment of their environment, we have added in the fox cages, cattle bone, balls and cardboard boxes.

3. Larval form production on intermediate host: mouse

Mice metacestodes production has been maintained during all the period, including COVID-19 confinement. During 2020-2021, 103 mice have been used. Sixty-nine mice (66%) developed larval form after infestation in the abdominal cavity or in the liver and among positive mice with larval form; forty-two (61%) have developed protoscolex.

The development of protoscolex has been observed; eight mice had immature form (19%), fourteen presented few protoscolexes (33%), whereas twenty have a high number of protoscolexes (48%).

Our experience in mice infection, have defined the optimal parameters for animal welfare, to obtain high level of protoscolexes after in intraperitoneal injection with *Echinococcus multilocularis* larval preparation. The chart reported below shows the production of protoscolexes in function of time post infestation and of the weight of the mouse at the date of euthanasia.

- High level of protoscoleces
- ◆ Low level of protoscoleces
- Immature protoscoleces

The best production of protoscoleces has been obtain between 4 to 6 months post infection with mice that weight between 40 to 70 g. Our new request (2022) for ethical authorisation for “experimental infection of mice with larval form of *Echinococcus multilocularis*” takes account of these observations and the limit of euthanasia of mice were define as 6 months after infestation and under the weight of 70 g.

⇒ Production:

Independent of perturbation due to COVID-19 pandemic, our production of larval has been use to infect nine batch of mice and three more that are in course. We have obtain a new strain from Zurich University that is also maintain in our animal facility.

The larval production has been use as internal standard for DNA extraction in our quality system. We have use protoscoleces when available for production of metacestodes reference material: 200 references DNA/protein samples are in stock and at the disposition for WP3. We perform also in five experimental infestation of foxes with protoscoleces (WP1-T3).

4. Worm and egg production on definitive host: Fox

For the production of reference material for the WP2, WP3, WP4, we have use seven foxes.

They were infected by oesophagiae intubation with a preparation of *E. multilocularis* protoscoleces produced in mice in our animal facilities from two strains (Anses, Zurich University).

Two different protocols have been taken in place:

One with euthanasia of animal at 28 dpi and intestine collect and decontaminated at -80°C as reference material to perform analyses by SSCT for the SSCT Proficiency Test for Meme partners.

A second with deworming treatment at 90 dpi with the collection of faecal samples to obtain reference positive faeces (with or without eggs) for our partners for future development of diagnostic protocol.

In the two protocols, feces have been collected daily and decontaminated at -80°C to perform PCR analyses in order to monitor the infection.

An infection of two red foxes was realized using *E. granulosus* s.s. cysts from slaughterhouses in order to obtain *E. granulosus* eggs to infect sheep in Portugal. The flotation and PCR results until 47 dpi were negative. Analyses of fecal samples by flotation between 60 and 70 dpi has confirm the absence of infection. Wether the red fox is a good host for *E. granulosus* s.s. is not known but was used in absence of the possibility to infect dogs in our animal facilities.

All experimental procedures are presented in this table.

Protocol	EJP1	EJP2	EJP3	EJP4	EJP5
Number of fox	2	1	2	1	1
<i>Echinococcus</i> strain	<i>E. multilocularis</i>	<i>E. multilocularis</i>	<i>E. granulosus</i>	<i>E. multilocularis</i>	<i>E. multilocularis</i>
Strain origin	Anses	Anses	IZS satdenia	Anses	Zurich university
Number of protoscoleces use for infestation	35,000	50,000	20,000	25,000	5,000
Time infestation	90 days	28 days	70 days	28 days	In course
Final status of fox	deworming	euthanasia	deworming	euthanasia	//
Sampling and use	Feces eggs	Intestine worm	No infection	Pre-patent Feces and worm	//

⇒ Production:

We have produced reference positive feces (with or without eggs) for partners for the development of diagnostic protocol. Fifty faeces are available and some new are in course.

A study about the detection of *E. multilocularis* DNA by corpo-qPCR during prepatent and patent infection has been done in order to obtain a better understanding of *E. multilocularis* DNA detection in fox feces.

Positive intestine have been use for PT SSCT.

5,000 eggs have been isolated from mature proglottides of worms or from faecal samples.

